

Study case Al-Alamein Military Museum, Egypt

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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution:

Al-Alamein Military Museum was founded on the 16th of December 1956, when the president Gamal Abd El-Nasser ordered its establishment to commemorate Egypt's role in Al-Alamein battles, held in 1942 between the Allies and the Axis. The Museum aims to document Al-Alamein battles by introducing a group of weapons, armors, and models which symbolize Al-Alamein battles and the contributing forces, besides a group of battle course-of-action maps, as well as acquisitions of battle commanders¹.

The museum is under direct tutelage of the Ministry of Defense.

Direct interview with the museum representatives could not take place, as it would have required preliminary authorization from the Egyptian government. Data about this case was gathered based on discussions with the RAF Museum (counterpart in the considered project) and articles in the media².

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

The study case concerns the wreck of a British Curtiss Kittyhawk, belonging 260 Squadron of the Royal Air Force, flown by Sergeant Dennis Copping. Plane and pilot went missing during a flight back to base on June 28, 1942.

The wreck was found in the Sahara Desert in 2012, by a Polish oil survey expedition. Except for the mechanical damage related to the crash, the aircraft had been preserved in very good condition. Most of the instruments, as well as armament and ammunition and various elements belonging to the pilot (parachute) were preserved. Human remains were not found immediately near the wreck, but further

¹ Sourced at : <https://www.mod.gov.eg/ModWebSite/MuseumDetails.aspx?id=3>, 02/09/2021.

² <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/article/120524-world-war-ii-plane-egypt-desert-science-p-40-lost>;
<https://warbirdsnews.com/warbirds-news/desert-war-kittyhawk-unveiled-in-egypt.html>;
<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-5231593/Egyptians-World-War-II-RAF-Kittyhawk-plane-makeover.html>

Sourced 02/09/2021

away in the desert. The Egyptian authorities have not been able to formally identify them as those of the pilot (this assumption has been disputed).

The wreck is legal property of the Egyptian government. Contact was made by the Royal Air Force Museum shortly after the recovery of the wreck, to find an agreement to bring it back to the UK, aiming to exhibit it as time-capsule in the museum.

Negotiations were difficult, due to the internal political and social turmoil Egypt was facing at the time. An emergency decision has been made to move the wreck from the recovery site in the desert and place it in safe storage. For this operation, the RAF gave mandate to a private third party (a British company specialized in restoring and operating WWII aircraft), in exchange for a surplus aircraft in the museum's collection.

After this move, negotiations to bring back the wreck to the UK could go no further, as the Egyptian government decided to keep the wreck and show it in the Al-Alamein Museum. The fate of the wreck remained unknown for a few years, until the aircraft was presented in the museum in 2017, fully restored and repainted (see fig. 1 and fig. 2 below).

Fig. 1 Wreck upon recovery in 2012 (© Jakub Perka)

Fig. 2 Aircraft after renovation in 2017 (© Steven Phipps)

• Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

No information available.

•Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

No direct information available.

According to information from RAF, it seems very unlikely that conservators or technical staff familiar with conservation of aircraft was involved in the project.

• Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

The aircraft is presented outdoors in the museum's courtyard. A Supermarine Spitfire Mk.Vc BR491 is also presented in the same conditions.

• Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

No information available.

• Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

No information available.

• Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

No direct information available.

Based on photographies found online, it appears some parts of the aircraft have been remade. The engine has been left outside the cockpit and is presented lying on the ground at the foot of the aircraft. The painting scheme is not accurate and does not correspond to the aircraft's original squadron livery.

• Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

The museum aims to present in an equal manner memories and artefacts from three of the foreign countries involved in the Al-Alamein battles : Great-Britain, Germany, Italy. There is also an Egyptian Hall, which documents Egypt's role in the conflict under British domination, and a Joint Hall, including artefacts from all the countries which were part of the conflict.

In the case of the Curtiss Kittyhawk wreck, choices made for restoration and presentation have been strongly connected with criteria unrelated to its material condition or its significance. It would also seem that identification and honoring the memory of the pilot has not been a priority.

The completion of this project was in line with the celebration of the 75th anniversary of the Second Battle of Al-Alamein. For the occasion, the museum and many of the military equipment pieces

presented in the collection underwent significant renovations. The ceremony was held in presence of General Abdel Fattah al-Sisi, Egypt's leader.

Both the course and the result of this project have been very controversial in the UK, at all stages. The fate of the wreck raised important public attention and has received wide media coverage. RAF Museum had to face strong criticism, for having "naively lost" one of their collection aircraft in the unsuccessful attempt to bring back the wreck to the UK. According to the RAF museum, criticism did not consider the fact that the museum had little leverage in the difficult diplomatic context and that the priority at the time was to protect the wreck from being subjected to looting.

Comments also touched upon subjects like the repatriation of cultural heritage and how the role suffered by Egypt in WWII could be used to serve contemporary political agenda.